

Studies in the Cyclohexane Series. Part VIII† The Confirmed Evidence for the Existence of Two Conformers of 4-Methylcyclohexane-1,1-dicarboxylic acids

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The two isomeric 1-carboxy-4-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acids have by a series of reactions been converted into their respective 4-methylcyclohexane-1,1-dicarboxylic acids and their identities confirmed by their unambiguous synthesis.

CONSIDERABLE amount of work has been carried out employing physical methods¹⁻⁸ which have established that the cyclohexane molecule predominantly exists in the chair form,⁹ which constantly flips into the boat form¹⁰ and vice-versa at a high frequency through an intermediate "twist form".¹¹ However, on the chemical side various investigators have made efforts to adduce evidences for the multiplanar forms of cyclohexane and their conclusions have invariably been of a conflicting nature.¹²

Desai, Hunter and Saharia¹³ reported the isolation of two isomeric forms of 4- and 3-methylcyclohexane-1,1-dicarboxylic acids which these workers in the light of the then existing knowledge, considered these to be the derivatives of the cyclohexane ring in the chair and the boat forms. These observations of Desai, Hunter and Saharia were later contradicted by Price¹⁴ et al., partly because their attempts to isolate the isomeric 4-methylcyclohexane-1,1-dicarboxylic acids failed. In order to refute their criticism, the entire work of Desai, Hunter and Saharia on the preparation of 4-methylcyclohexane-1,1-dicarboxylic acids has been repeated, and their earlier findings have been confirmed. The validity of this method also gets support from the work of Saharia^{15,16} et al., on the preparation of cyclohexane- and cycloheptane-1,1-dicarboxylic acids.

The identities of these isomeric acids have also been established by independent and unambiguous synthesis, which consisted in condensing diethyl malonate with 3-methyl-1, 5-dibromopentane in presence of sodium ethoxide and subsequent hydrolysis of diethyl 4-methylcyclohexane-1,1-dicarboxylate. Two isomeric acids having melting points identical with the isomeric 4-methylcyclohexane-1,1-dicarboxylic acids prepared by the oxidation of the corresponding glycollic acids (II; R₂ = OH) were obtained; mixed

melting points of the above acids prepared by two separate routes showed no depression.

A; R = H; R₁ = CH₃
B; R = CH₃; R₁ = H

The two isomeric 1-carboxy-4-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acids (IA & B), their monobromo acids (IIA & B; R₂ = Br) and the glycollic acids (IIA & B; R₂ = OH) were prepared according to the methods already described¹³. The bromo acids were accompanied by their anhydrides (IVA & B) identified by their elemental analysis and IR spectra. The existence of the glycollic acids, obtained by the hydrolysis of the bromo acids, was challenged by Price et al (loc. cit.) according to whom these acids were the lactonic acids but the equivalent weights of the acids, their analytical and IR spectral data show that these are dibasic hydroxy acids.

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The controlled alkaline potassium permanganate oxidation (6 hrs) of these glycollic acids furnished the glyoxalic acids which were characterised by their equivalent weights, analytical and IR spectral

cyclohexane-1, 1-dicarboxylic acids (IIIA & B). These were characterised by their equivalent weights, analytical & IR spectral data and by the preparation of their diethyl esters and diamides.

Fig. 1. I.R. spectrum of IIA

Fig. 2. I.R. spectrum of IIB

Fig. 3 I.R. spectrum of IIIA

Fig. 4. I.R. spectrum of IIIB

data and formation of quinoxaline derivatives, while their prolonged oxidation (18 hrs) furnished 4-methyl-

Thus, we affirm without any hesitation that the experimental results of Desai, Hunter and Saharia

(loc. cit.) are correct and fail to understand how Price et al., could not repeat these observations.

In order to distinguish between the two conformers of 4-methyl-cyclohexane-1, 1-dicarboxylic acids, the diethyl esters of 1-carboxy-4-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acids were prepared, their boiling points and refractive indices determined which are given in the Table below. The boiling points of the two isomers A and B will be different according to the nature of the methyl group and the hydrogen atom fixed at C-4 which may be axial or equatorial, keeping the nature of the group -COOEt as axial and -CH₂-COOEt as equatorial at C-1. According to van Arkel,¹⁷ and Éliel and Haber¹⁸, those esters which have got the maximum number of equatorial groups would have higher boiling point than their axial conformers. The diethyl ester of the acid IA, m.p. 173° having higher boiling point should have its methyl group equatorial and, therefore, the acid IB, m.p. 137° shall have the methyl group in the axial position.

Therefore, the 4-methylcyclohexane-1, 1-dicarboxylic acid IIIA, m.p. 171° resulting from the acid IA, m.p. 173° is the one in which the methyl group is equatorial because the nature of the groups at C-1 are the same and the other 1, 1-dicarboxylic acid IIIB, m.p. 176°, obtained from the acid IB, m.p. 137° will be the one having the methyl group axial.

The above conclusion in respect of the boiling point rule is further supported by the modified von Auwers-Skita rule of Allinger¹⁹ based upon the refractive indices of the diethyl esters of the acids IA and B. According to this rule the conformer having the higher refractive index is the one in which there are maximum number of axial groups, thus the diethyl ester of the acid IB has higher refractive index than that of the acid IA and, therefore, the acid IA has the methyl group equatorial at C-4 and the acid IB has the methyl group axial at C-4. From the evidence of the boiling points and refractive indices, we conclude that 4-methylcyclohexane-1, 1-dicarboxylic acid IIA, m.p. 171° has the methyl group equatorial at C-4 while the other conformer IIIB, m.p. 176° has the methyl group axial at C-4.

TABLE

No.	Name of the ester	Boiling point °C	Refractive index
1.	Ethyl 4-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxylate-1-acetate(A)	156/7.5 mm	$n_D^{27} 1.4515$
2.	 (B)	115/6.8 mm	$n_D^{27} 1.4635$
3.	Ethyl 4-methylcyclohexane-1, 1-dicarboxylate (A)	120/2.5 mm	$n_D^{27} 1.4615$
4.	 (B)	105/5 mm	$n_D^{27} 1.4750$

Experimental

1-Carboxy 4-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid, m.p. 125-140° in 93.8% yield was prepared following the

procedure employed by Saharia et al.^{15,16}. The separation of the acids IA and B, their bromination and subsequent alkaline hydrolysis to the respective 1-carboxy-4-methylcyclohexane-1-glycollic acids were carried out in the manner described in our earlier communication.¹³ The bromoanhydrides (IV) of the bromo acids formed to a small extent were removed by treatment with *n*-hexane.

A-series

(a) 1-Carboxy 4-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid. (IA) had m.p. 173° (Found : C, 60.0; H, 7.9. C₁₀H₁₆O₄ requires C, 60.0; H, 8.0%) IR γ_{max}^{Nujol} 1715 cm⁻¹.

(b) 1-Carboxy 4-methylcyclohexane-1- α -bromoacetic acid (IIA; R₂ = Br) had m.p. 152° (Yield, 89.6%). (Found : C, 43.2; H, 5.3; equiv, 139.2 C₁₀H₁₅O₄Br requires C, 43.0; H, 5.4%); 139.5-dibasic). IR γ_{max}^{Nujol} 1720 cm⁻¹.

(c) The bromo anhydride (IVA) had m.p. 101° (Found : C, 46.1; H, 5.1. C₁₀H₁₈O₃Br requires C, 46.0; H, 5.0%). IR γ_{max}^{Nujol} 1869, 1795 cm⁻¹.

(d) 1-Carboxy-4-methylcyclohexane-1-glycollic acid (IIA, R₂ = OH) had m.p. 134° (yield, 60.5%). (Found : C, 55.5; H, 7.6; equiv, 107.8. C₁₀H₁₆O₅ requires C, 55.6; H, 7.4%; 108-dibasic) (Yield, 60.1%). IR γ_{max}^{Nujol} 3630, 1700 cm⁻¹.

(e) 1-Carboxy-4-methylcyclohexane-1-glyoxalic acid

The glycollic acid (IIA; R₂ = OH; 2.0 g) dissolved in water (50 ml) was made just alkaline with aqueous barium hydroxide (N/20) and potassium permanganate (2 g in water, 200 ml) added during 3 hrs while stirring which was continued for five more hours. The contents, after treatment with sulphuric dioxide and acidification, were continuously extracted with ether (12 hrs) the ethereal solution on working up gave a residue which solidified in vacuum and had m.p. 115°-6°. On crystallisation from benzene-petrol (60°-80°), the pure acid melted at 112°. (Yield : 1.5g; 75.7%) (Found : C, 56.2; H, 6.4; equiv, 106.8. C₁₀H₁₄O₅ requires C, 56.0; H, 6.5%; 107-dibasic) IR γ_{max}^{Nujol} 1720 cm⁻¹.

Its *quinoxaline* derivative had m.p. 230°. (Found : C, 67.0; H, 6.1. C₁₆H₁₆O₃N₂ requires C, 67.1; H, 6.3%).

(f) 4-methylcyclohexane-1, 1-dicarboxylic acid (IIIA) had m.p. 171° (Yield, 52.3%). (Found : C, 58.3; H, 7.6%; equiv, 92.8. C₉H₁₄O₄ requires C, 58.1; H, 7.5%; 93.0-dibasic). IR γ_{max}^{Nujol} 1724, 1701 cm⁻¹. Mixed m.p. with acid IA (2 : 1) and (1 : 1) was depressed to 151.2° and 155.6° respectively; mixed m.p. with acid IIIB, m.p. 176° was depressed to 138°-9°. Ethyl 4-methylcyclohexane-1, 1-dicarboxylate had b.p. 120°/2.5 mm (Yield, 79.4%). (Found : C, 64.7; H, 9.0. C₁₃H₂₂O₄ requires C, 64.5; H, 9.1%) I.R. γ_{max}^{KBr} 1739 cm⁻¹. 4-methylcyclohexane-1, 1-dicarboxylic acid diamide had m.p. 243°. (Found : C, 58.6; H, 8.6. C₉H₁₆O₂N₂ requires C, 58.7; H, 8.7%)

B-Series

(a) 1-Carboxy-4-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid (IB) had m.p. 137°. (Found : C, 59.9; H, 8.0. $C_{10}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 60.0; H, 8.0%) IR γ_{max}^{Nujol} 1706 cm^{-1} .

(b) 1-Carboxy 4-methylcyclohexane-1- α -bromoacetic acid (IIB; $R_2 = Br$) had m.p. 132° (Yield, 87.8%). (Found : C 43.2; H, 5.3; equiv, 139.4. $C_{10}H_{15}O_4Br$ requires C, 43.0; H, 5.4%; 139.5-dibasic) IR γ_{max}^{Nujol} 1720 cm^{-1} .

(c) The bromoanhydride (IVB) had m.p. 83°. (Found : C, 46.1; H, 4.9. $C_{10}H_{13}O_3Br$ requires C, 46.0; H, 5.0%) IR γ_{max}^{Nujol} 1869, 1795 cm^{-1} .

(d) 1-Carboxy-4-methylcyclohexane-1-glycollic acid (IIB; $R_2 = OH$), had m.p. 144°-5° (Yield, 64.7%). (Found : C, 55.8; H, 7.6; equiv, 107.9. $C_{10}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 55.6; H, 7.5%; 108-dibasic) IR γ_{max}^{Nujol} 3630, 1700 cm^{-1} .

(e) 1-Carboxy-4-methylcyclohexane-1-glyoxalic acid was prepared in the manner shown above and crystallised from benzene-ethyl acetate had m.p. 102°. (Yield, 53.7%). (Found : C, 56.1; H, 6.3; equiv. 106.9. $C_{10}H_{14}O_5$ requires. C. 56.0; H, 6.5%; 107-dibasic).

Its quinoxaline derivative had m.p. 204°. (Found : C, 66.9; H, 6.0; $C_{16}H_{18}O_3N_2$ requires C, 67.1; H, 6.3%).

(f) 4-Methylcyclohexane-1, 1-dicarboxylic acid (IIIB) had m.p. 176° (Yield, 47.0%). (Found : C, 58.3; H, 7.4; equiv, 92.8. $C_9H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 58.1; H, 7.5%; 93. -dibasic). IR γ_{max}^{Nujol} 1724, 1701 cm^{-1} . Mixed m.p. with acid IB, m.p. 137° (1:1) and (2:1) depressed to 115°-6° and 121°-2° respectively; mixed m.p. with the acid IIIA, m.p. 171° was depressed to 140°-1°. Ethyl 4-methylcyclohexane-1, 1-dicarboxylate had b.p. 105°/5mm n_D^{27} 1.4750. (Found : C, 64.4; H, 9.3. $C_{13}H_{22}O_4$ requires C. 64.5; H, 9.1%). IR γ_{max}^{Film} 1739 cm^{-1} . 4-Methylcyclohexane-1, 1-dicarboxylic acid diamide had m.p. 187°. (Found : C, 58.6; H, 8.5. $C_9H_{16}O_2M_2$ requires C. 58.7; H, 8.7%).

Synthesis of 4-methylcyclohexane-1, 1-dicarboxylic acids

3-Methyl-1, 5-dibromopentane (24.4g; 0.01 mole) prepared from 4-methylpiperidine, on condensation with diethyl malonate (16.0g; 0.1 mole) in presence of sodium ethoxide gave ethyl 4-methylcyclohexane-1, 1-dicarboxylate, b.p. 147°-150°/10 mm. (Yield; 14.56g; 60.0%). (Found : C, 64.8; H, 9.0. $C_{13}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 64.5; H, 9.1%). IR γ_{max}^{Film} 1739 cm^{-1} .

The above ester (8.0 g) was refluxed with aqueous potassium hydroxide (20%; 100 ml) for 24 hrs. the alkaline extract acidified and continuously extracted with ether. The ethereal layer on working up gave a residue which solidified in vacuum (24 hrs) and had m.p. 154°-9°. On fractional crystallisation from

benzene-ethyl acetate two acids having m.ps 171° and 176° in yields of 56.9% and 7.3% respectively were obtained. The former was identified having the structure IIIA as it did not depress the m.p. of IIIA obtained by degradation of the acid IA and the latter was recognized as acid IIIB since it gave no depression in m.p. with the acid IIIB

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